

ARTISTIC EXPRESSION IN MAVLONO ATOIY'S GHAZALS AND TUYUKS

Normatova Lobar Dilshod qizi

Student of Shakhrisabz State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation: This article explores the work of Mavlono Atoiy, his place in classical Uzbek literature, and his artistic mastery. The folk style, simple language, aruz meter, and the use of tajnis (homonymy) employed in the poet's ghazals and tuyuks are analyzed using examples. The essence of Atoiy's poetry and the experiences of the lyrical hero are also revealed.

Keywords: Mavlono Atoiy, classical literature, ghazal, tuyuk, tajnis, aruz, lyrics, artistic skill.

One of the prominent representatives of our classical literature, Mavlono Atoiy, lived and created in the 15th century. He lived in Samarkand, Bukhara, and Balkh and wrote in both Turkic and Persian languages. Alisher Navoi, in his work "Nasoyim ul-Muhabbat" ("Breezes of Friendship"), writes about Mavlono Atoiy as follows: "Mavlono Atoiy was from Balkh. He was from the descendants of Ismail Ata (the son of Ibrahim Ata, the younger brother of Ahmad Yassawi). He was a dervish-like, good-natured, and open-faced person. In his time, his poetry gained great fame among the Turkic-speaking peoples. This matla' (first couplet) is his: That idol sits by the water like a fairy,

So delicate that even water would be too much if one were to swallow it.

There is a flaw in its rhyme. However, Mavlono composed much in the Turkic style. He was not overly concerned with the strict requirements of rhyme. His grave is in the vicinity of Balkh."

In the preface of Atoiy's devon (collected poems) and at the end of the manuscript, it is referred to as "Devoni Shaykhzoda Atoiy" (The Devon of Shaykhzoda Atoiy). This is cited as evidence of his descent from a family of sheikhs. According to Navoi, Atoiy also served in the court of Mirzo Ulugbek. Atoiy is known to have composed in many genres of his time. However, among these, the ghazal and tuyuk genres are considered the most prolific in his work. The theme of love is widely explored in Atoiy's ghazals. Alongside love, the theme of wine is also addressed, celebrating the joy of life and all its beauties. Atoiy's lyricism abounds with folk expressions, idioms, proverbs, sayings, and words related to fairy-tale themes. He primarily composed his ghazals in the ramal meter of aruz (prosody); the rhythm is light, the verses short, the words simple, and the style plain and fluent. This is precisely why many of his poems

transformed into folk songs. Atoiy also created artistic devices and techniques such as tajohuli orifona (pretended ignorance) and laf va nashr (synthesis and distribution). In his tuyuks, we witness his masterful use of the tajnis (homonymy) art.

"Kechamen" (I'm passing / This night I...)

Bodasiz betobmen bu kecha men,

La'ling istab emdi jondin kechamen.

Sohili maqsadg'a yetgaymanmu deb,

Ko'z yoshim daryosida suv kechamen.

In this tuyuk, the tajnis (homonymy) art is created through the phrases "kecha men" (this night I) and "kechamen" (I pass / forsake). Their meanings are as follows:

- In the first line: "bu kecha men" – here kecha means "night," i.e., "tonight."
- In the second line: "jondin kechamen" – here the verb kechmoq is used, meaning "to forsake" or "to sacrifice."
- In the fourth line: "suv kechamen" – here again the verb is used, but it means "to wade through water" (to traverse).

General analysis of the tuyuk:

- Line 1: Tonight, I am unwell without (the) wine (of your love).
- Line 2: Longing for your ruby-like lips, I am now ready to forsake (sacrifice) my very life.
- Line 3: Wondering whether I will reach the shore of my desire (your union)...
- Line 4: I am wading through the river formed by my own tears.

The lyrical hero sheds so many tears in his path to reach the beloved that these tears form a river. He wades through this river of tears to reach the "shore of his goal" (the beloved) and is willing to sacrifice his life in this journey.

"Yonamen" (I Burn / Again I)

Dilrabo, hajring o'tida yonamen,

O'rtanib vasling tilarman yona men.

Ka'ba azmidin manga sen muddao,

Bo'lmasang, albatta, andin yonamen.

In this tuyuk, the word "yonamen" appears in three different meanings, creating tajnis:

- In the first line: "o'tida yonamen" – here yonmoq is the verb "to burn."
- In the second line: "yona men" – here yona (another form of yana, meaning "again") combines with the pronoun "men" (I), meaning "I, once more."
- In the fourth line: "andin yonamen" – here yonmoq is used meaning "to turn back" or "to retreat."

General analysis of the tuyuk:

- Line 1: O charmer (dilrabo), I burn in the fire of your separation.
- Line 2: Scorched by this, I wish for your union once again.
- Line 3: For me, you are the ultimate goal, more than the intention to visit the Kaaba.
- Line 4: If you are not there, I will certainly turn back from that place.

The lover burns so intensely in the fire of separation that even his primary aim in embarking on a sacred journey is to find his beloved. For the lover, the beloved's vision surpasses everything else. He declares his readiness to turn back if he does not encounter the beloved at his destination.

"Ot" (Horse / Shoot / Name)

*Jilva aylab sakraturda sarkash ot,
Noz o'qin javlon etib jonimg'a ot.
Itlaring xaylig'a xizmat ayladim,
Qo'ydilar ahli vafo deb manga ot.*

In this tuyuk, the word "ot" appears in three different meanings, creating tajnis:

- In the first line: "sarkash ot" – here ot means "horse."
- In the second line: "jonimg'a ot" – here ot is the verb otmoq, meaning "to shoot."
- In the fourth line: "manga ot" – here ot means "name" or "title."

General analysis of the tuyuk:

- Line 1: (My beloved) prances on a spirited, unruly horse, showing off her grace.
- Line 2: While doing so, shoot the arrow of coquetry (her eyelashes or gaze) towards my soul.

- Line 3: I served the pack of dogs at your doorstep faithfully.
- Line 4: As a result, people gave me the name "faithful one."

The lyrical hero is mesmerized by the beloved's graceful display on horseback and wishes for her playful glances to strike his heart. The lover considers himself among the dogs at the beloved's gate (which in classical poetry signifies supreme loyalty). Consequently, he expresses that he has earned the reputation of being a loyal lover among people.

"O't" (Fire / Grass / Pass)

*Sham' yanglig' yonadur boshimda o't,
Ko'z yoshimdin yer yuzinda undi o't.
Qon yoshim qildi yo'lungni lolazor,
Muncha taqsir ayladim, qonimdan o't.*

In this tuyuk, the word "o't" is used in three different meanings:

- In the first line: "boshimda o't" – here o't means "fire."
- In the second line: "undi o't" – here o't means "grass."
- In the fourth line: "qonimdan o't" – here o't is the verb o'tmoq, meaning "to forgive" or "to overlook." General analysis of the tuyuk:
- Line 1: (In your love) fire burns on my head like a candle.
- Line 2: From my tears, grass has sprouted on the face of the earth.
- Line 3: My bloody tears have turned your path into a field of tulips.
- Line 4: Forgive my sins, overlook my faults, as many as I have committed.

The lyrical hero uses hyperbole to depict the intensity of his love-sickness. His head is aflame, and his tears are so abundant they cause grass to grow. In the final line, he pleads with the beloved for forgiveness for his transgressions. In classical poetry, "qonidan o'tmoq" (to pass from one's blood) also signifies forgoing a death sentence or forgiving a great sin.

In conclusion, Mavlono Atoiy, as a prominent representative of classical Uzbek literature, made a significant contribution to the development of Turkic poetry through his work. His works harmoniously blend a simple and fluent style, folk spirit, deep lyricism, and artistic mastery. Atoiy was particularly prolific in the ghazal and tuyuk genres, portraying love, human emotions, and the zest for life through unique artistic expressions. Key aspects of his work

include his closeness to the vernacular language, his extensive use of idioms and proverbs, and the light meter of his poems. Therefore, his works quickly gained popularity among the people and have lived on as songs. In his tuyuks, Atoiy masterfully employed the art of tajnis (homonymy), achieving the expression of multiple meanings through a single word, thereby imbuing his tuyuks with profound artistry.

List of Used Literature:

1. *Navoi, Alisher. Nasoyim ul-muhabbat.*
2. *Atoiy. Devoni Shayxzoda Atoiy.*
3. *Qayumov, A. History of Uzbek Literature.*
4. *Rasulov, A. History of Classical Uzbek Poetry.*
5. *Sultonov, I. Theory of Literature.*
6. *Yoqubov, O. Literary Heritage and Interpretation.*
7. *G'aniyev, I. Introduction to Classical Literature.*
8. *Is'hoqov, Y. The Art of Language and Fundamentals of Artistry.*